

Charge-transfer complexes of ofloxacin, chlorpheniramine, azacyclonol and indapamide drugs with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzoquinone

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Abstract : Charge-transfer (CT) complexes of ofloxacin, chlorpheniramine, azacyclonol and indapamide drugs with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzoquinone (DDQ) were investigated spectrophotometrically in different organic solvents at different temperatures. The spectral characteristics and formation constants of the formed 1 : 1 CT-complexes were examined and discussed in terms of the solvent properties. The oscillator and transition dipole strengths of the complexes have been determined from the CT absorption spectra. The ΔH^0 , ΔS^0 and ΔG^0 values are all negative, indicating stability and exothermic character of the complexes. The ionization potential value of the donors calculated using spectral data are in good agreement with those computed using molecular orbital package MOPAC (PM3) method. Infrared analysis of the CT-complexes have also been carried out.

Keywords : Charge-transfer, solvent effect, MOPAC method, drugs, electronic spectra, molecular complexes.

Introduction

Quinones are one of the well known electron acceptors¹ that give rise to spectacular charge-transfer (CT) complexes with variety of donors. The study of quinones for their CT-interactions stems from their possible role in biological reactions. Quinones are known to be important in many biological fields². Thus, the mechanism of charge-transfer to the quinones, in general, is a research topic of significant interest.

The survey of the literature reveals that the studies on the spectroscopic and other physico-chemical aspects of the CT-complexes formed by organic^{1,3-7} and drug molecules⁸⁻¹³ are well documented. Further, the studies on the CT-complexes of drugs are significant as the principle of CT-complex formation has been successfully utilized in pharmaceutical estimation of drugs¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

In continuation of our earlier work on the study of solvent effect on the CT-complex of a drug with DDQ^{13,19}, the work of the present article is devoted to a detailed study of CT-complexes of ofloxacin, chlorpheniramine, azacyclonol and indapamide drugs with a π -electron acceptor, DDQ. Chlorpheniramine and azacyclonol are antihistamines. Ofloxacin is an antibacterial drug and indapamide is an antibiotic drug. The spectral characteristics of the CT-bands, the equilibrium and thermodynamic parameters of the formed CT-complexes were evaluated and discussed. To the best of our knowledge this is

the first report on the systematic study on the CT-interaction of these drugs.

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics of the CT-bands :

The electronic spectra of CT-complexes of the donors with DDQ were recorded using constant acceptor concentration (in a given solvent) and varying concentrations of a donor depending on the solvent, but always $[D] > [A]$. The electronic spectra were scanned against the electron acceptor concentration as in the test solution to eliminate the possible overlap that may arise between CT-complexes band and that of the acceptor. In all the cases under investigation, the absorption spectra of solutions containing both donor and acceptor together exhibit new absorptions at longer wavelengths than either the donors or the acceptor alone. The new and low energy absorptions indicate the formation of CT-complexes and a representative CT-spectra is shown in Fig. 1. The wavelength, CT-energy, frequency and wave number corresponding to the absorption maxima of the complexes were given in Table 1.

Formation constants and molar extinction coefficients of the CT-complexes :

The formation constants (K) and molar extinction coefficients (ϵ) of the studied CT-complexes in all the solvents were determined spectrophotometrically in the

Fig. 1. The UV-Vis absorption spectra of azacyclonol-DDQ solutions in DMSO at 298 K. [Azacyclonol] = 6.0891×10^{-3} M; [DDQ] = 7.9292×10^{-4} M.

Table 1. The absorption maxima of the CT-complexes in different solvents at 298 K

Solvent	λ_{\max} (nm)	$h\nu_{CT}$ (eV)	$10^{14} \nu_{\max}$ (s ⁻¹)	$\bar{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)
Ofloxacin-DDQ				
Ethyl acetate	454	2.73	6.61	22026
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	463	2.68	6.48	21598
Acetone	459	2.70	6.54	21786
DMF	478	2.60	6.28	20921
DMSO	468	2.65	6.41	21368
Chloropheniramine-DDQ				
Dichloromethane	462	2.68	6.49	21645
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	463	2.68	6.48	21598
DMF	475	2.61	6.32	21053
Acetonitrile	458	2.71	6.55	21834
DMSO	468	2.65	6.41	21368
Azacyclonol-DDQ				
Benzene	433	2.87	6.93	23095
Chlorobenzene	398	3.12	7.54	25126
Acetone	360	3.45	8.33	27778
DMF	365	3.40	8.22	27397
DMSO	386	3.21	7.77	25907
Indapamide-DDQ				
Dichloromethane	350	3.55	8.57	28571
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	346	3.59	8.67	28902
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	348	3.57	8.62	28736
Acetonitrile	345	3.60	8.70	28986

temperature range 298–313 K using the Scott equation²⁰. The K and ϵ values obtained are given in Table 2. The results reveal that in all the solvents the formation constant decreases with increase in temperature indicating the exothermic nature of the interaction between the donor drugs and the electron acceptor. Further, the observed high value of K suggests that the formed CT-complexes are of a strong type. The stoichiometry of the CT-complexes of the electron donors with the acceptor was determined by applying Job's method of continuous

Table 2. Formation constant (K , dm³ mol⁻¹) and the molar extinction coefficient (ϵ , dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) for the CT-complexes as a function of relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of the solvent and temperature (T , Kelvin)

Solvent	ϵ_r	T	K	ϵ
Ofloxacin-DDQ				
Ethyl acetate	6.02	298	11812	909
		305	7162	909
		313	2924	1171
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	12.47	298	9181	2084
		305	8602	2585
		313	4665	2623
Acetone	20.70	298	9001	1237
		305	7361	1142
		313	5028	1140
DMF	36.71	298	7161	769
		305	5166	667
		313	4052	769
DMSO	46.68	298	9702	1047
		305	8681	1000
		313	8427	1176
Chloropheniramine-DDQ				
Dichloromethane	8.93	298	8050	2505
		305	2328	2694
		313	404	2409
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	12.47	298	4544	2399
		305	1323	2379
		313	394	2149
DMF	36.71	298	1642	1039
		305	667	1060
		313	635	1058
Acetonitrile	37.5	298	470	1579
		305	336	1611
		313	201	1827
DMSO	46.68	298	530	833
		305	352	909
		313	330	833
Azacyclonol-DDQ				
Benzene	2.275	298	1573	6839
		305	1080	5271
		313	559	6669
Chlorobenzene	5.62	298	9102	10152
		305	4201	10504
		313	3720	11672

Table 2 (contd.)

Acetone	20.70	298	1677	20149
		305	1373	22823
		313	1193	24203
DMF	36.71	298	1182	14075
		305	912	14622
		313	756	15025
DMSO	46.68	298	1458	1722
		305	1446	1662
		313	1388	1589
Indapamide-DDQ				
Dichloromethane	8.93	298	9305	30778
		305	5279	35438
		313	4541	38752
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	12.47	298	2530	25965
		305	1742	28962
		313	1371	31471
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	17.93	298	3297	35791
		305	2689	37562
		313	2462	35235
Acetonitrile	37.5	298	4644	27999
		305	3825	30888
		313	3666	31388

variation²¹ and in the present study, this is found to be independent of solvent and temperature.

Thermodynamic parameters of the CT-complexes :

The variation of formation constants with temperature may be used to determine the thermodynamic parameters of the complexes. These thermodynamic parameters were obtained from the familiar van't Hoff plots (not shown)

Fig. 2. Relation between enthalpy and entropy changes for the CT-complexes of donors with DDQ.

are summarized in Table 3. The negative Gibbs energies indicate that the complex formation is thermodynamically favored, while the negative entropy indicates a decrease in the degree of freedom of the components upon complexation. Generally ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 become more and more negative as the stability constant for molecular complexation increases^{4,19}. The high negative value of ΔH^0 and the larger values of formation constants are indicators of strength of binding between donor and acceptor and the high stability of the resultant CT-complexes, as observed in the present study²². Thus a linear correlation between ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 is found for the CT-complexes in the present study (Fig. 2).

Solvent effect :

Mulliken and Person²³ have pointed out that the enthalpy of formation is more closely related to the stabilization due to charge transfer forces and thus related to strength of the complex. The results in Table 3 indicate that the magnitude of enthalpy of formation of charge transfer complexes is strongly dependent on the nature of

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of CT-complexes in different solvents

Solvent	$-\Delta H^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^0$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Ofloxacin-DDQ			
Ethyl acetate	66.0	143.3	23.3
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	32.7	3.2	22.8
Acetone	27.6	16.7	22.6
DMF	26.4	15.2	21.9
DMSO	6.4	-54.6	22.7
Chlorpheniramine-DDQ			
Dichloromethane	154.8	444.4	22.4
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	126.2	353.8	20.8
DMF	48.4	102.1	18.0
Acetonitrile	43.9	95.9	15.3
DMSO	24.1	29.3	15.4
Azacyclonol-DDQ			
Benzene	53.7	118.5	18.3
Chlorobenzene	45.7	78.5	22.3
Acetone	17.6	-2.7	18.4
DMF	23.0	18.6	17.5
DMSO	2.54	52.1	18.1
Indapamide-DDQ			
Dichloromethane	36.7	47.9	22.4
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	31.5	40.9	19.3
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	15.0	-16.8	20.0
Acetonitrile	12.1	29.4	20.8

Fig. 3. Plot of $-\Delta H^0$ of the ofloxacin-DDQ CT-complex vs the solubility parameter of the solvents.

the solvent for a given donor. This reflects the high sensitivity of the strength of the CT-complexes or the strength of the donor-acceptor interaction to the nature of the solvent.

The results in Table 3 indicate that as the relative permittivity of the medium increases, $-\Delta H^0$ decreases. The correlation between $-\Delta H^0$ and ϵ_r is satisfactory and the correlation coefficients for the donors I-IV are 0.86, 0.99, 0.92 and 0.84, respectively. Such an observed satisfactory correlation in all likelihood may be as a result of specific solvent-solute interactions²⁴. As the solubility parameter of the solvents is directly dependent on the vaporization energy and the molar volume of the solvent²⁵, the decrease in $-\Delta H^0$ can be correlated with both the dielectric and cage effects of the solvent. Hence an attempt was made to correlate the enthalpy change with solubility parameter, δ , of the solvents. The solubility parameter values used in this study were taken from the literature²⁶. The correlation of $-\Delta H^0$ with δ is excellent, with correlation coefficients for the donors I-IV are 0.97,

Table 4. Spectral properties of the CT-complexes in different solvents

Solvent	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$	f	μ	b^2/a^2	I_p (eV)	w (eV)
Ofloxacin-DDQ						
Ethyl acetate	5528.7	0.0217	1.4471	0.12	9.11	4.465
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	4430.6	0.0399	1.9809	0.22	9.04	4.453
Acetone	5399.8	0.0289	1.6735	0.13	9.07	4.458
DMF	6454.1	0.0214	1.4758	0.07	8.94	4.434
DMSO	4480.4	0.0194	1.4169	0.17	8.87	4.422
Chloropheniramine-DDQ						
Dichloromethane	2541	0.028	1.643	0.32	9.05	4.454
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	4312	0.045	2.096	0.22	9.04	4.453
DMF	7884	0.035	1.890	0.07	8.96	4.438
Acetonitrile	3231	0.022	1.465	0.17	9.08	4.460
DMSO	4902	0.018	1.325	0.17	9.01	4.447
Azacyclonol-DDQ						
Benzene	5252	0.155	3.778	0.19	9.27	4.495
Chlorobenzene	7236	0.317	5.180	0.15	9.57	4.552
Acetone	4372	0.381	5.395	0.05	9.98	4.626
DMF	6095	0.371	5.361	0.07	9.92	4.615
DMSO	3488	0.026	1.459	0.01	9.70	4.573
Indapamide-DDQ						
Dichloromethane	3460.8	0.4601	5.8493	0.11	10.10	4.648
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	9654.3	1.0829	8.9219	0.09	10.15	4.657
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	4822.8	0.7457	7.4249	0.04	10.13	4.652
Acetonitrile	4654.0	0.5629	6.4233	0.03	10.17	4.659

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectra of the CT-complexes of the donors with DDQ.

0.98, 0.95 and 0.96 respectively, suggesting that the strength of the CT-complexes is dependent on both the dielectric and cage effects of the solvent²⁵ and a representative plot is shown in Fig. 3. Further the decrease in $-\Delta H^0$ values with increase in relative permittivity of the medium may also be due to a second equilibrium between the solvent and donor molecule.

Spectral properties of the CT-complexes :

The values of oscillator strength (f) which is a measure of integrated intensity of the CT-band²⁷ and transition dipole moment (μ), were calculated by using the approximate equations²⁸ given in eqs. (2) and (3), where ϵ_{\max} is the molar extinction coefficient of the CT-complex at the wavelength of maximum absorption and $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ is the half band-width in wave number units. The values of f and μ thus obtained are given in Table 4.

$$f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} [\epsilon_{\max} \Delta\nu_{1/2}] \quad (2)$$

$$\mu = 0.0958 [\epsilon_{\max} \Delta\nu_{1/2} / \bar{\nu}_{\max}]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

The values of f are rather relatively large indicating a strong interaction between the donor-acceptor pairs with relative high probabilities of CT-transitions. This is supported by the relatively large heat of formation values. Further, the results in Table 4 indicate that the magnitude of f and hence the intensity of the CT-band is solvent dependent.

According to Mulliken's theory²⁹, the ratio b^2/a^2 between the coefficient of the dative structure to the non-bond structure wave functions ($\Psi_{D^+A^-}$ and $\Psi_{D^-A^+}$, respectively) was calculated. The ratios obtained (Table 4) are comparable to that of many strong CT-com-

plexes^{3,19,30,31}. This substantiates the strong nature inferred for the drugs-DDQ CT-complexes formed.

Ionization potential of the donor :

Out of the many applications of CT-complexes, one important application is to calculate the ionization potential of the donor. The ionization potential (I_p) of the highest filled molecular orbital of the donor was estimated from CT energies of its complexes with the acceptor making use of the empirical equations reported in the literature¹.

The calculated I_p values for molecular orbital participating in CT-interaction of the drugs are listed in Table 4. A comparison of the transition energies of the CT-complexes with the ionization potential values of the electron donor, in different solvents, reveals a regular relationship which is in accordance with the results obtained by McConnell *et al.*³². The ionization potential values of I-IV calculated by MOPAC (PM3) method are 8.81, 9.08, 9.67 and 10.18 eV respectively. In the present study, the average ionization potential values, calculated from spectral data, of I-IV were found to be 9.01, 9.03, 9.69 and 10.14 eV, respectively. It is interesting to note that the theoretical and experimental ionization potential values are in good agreement with each other and a plot (not shown) of $I_{p_{\text{cal}}}$ versus $I_{p_{\text{exp}}}$ is linear with $r = 0.99$; $sd = 0.12$ and unit slope.

Further evidence for the nature of CT-interaction in the present systems is the calculation of the dissociation energy (W) of the charge-transfer excited state of the complex in different solvents. The dissociation energies of the complex were calculated from their CT-energy,

Fig. 5. CO stretching frequency of CT-complexes of DDQ with donor drugs vs ionization potential of the donors.

$h\nu_{CT}$, the ionization potential of the donor, I_p and electron affinity, E^A of the acceptor using the empirical relation³² given in eq. (4).

$$h\nu_{CT} = I_p - E^A - W \quad (4)$$

The calculated values of W are given in Table 4. The acquired values of dissociation energy of charge-transfer excited states of the complex in different solvents are constant, which suggests that the investigated complex is reasonably strong and stable under the studied conditions with higher resonance stabilization energy⁴.

FT-IR spectral studies :

To get a better insight into the extent and nature of CT-interactions between the donors and DDQ, FT-IR spectral studies has been carried out. Charge transfer complexes of DDQ with donor drugs were prepared for infrared spectroscopic analysis as described in literature³³ using chloroform as solvent. FT-IR of the CT-complexes was taken using a JASCO FT-IR 460 Plus spectrometer.

Generally, the stretching vibrations of the complexed functional groups of the molecules decrease in wave number, whereas those of the out-of-plane vibrations increase³⁴. According to the characteristic patterns of the shifted infrared bands, one can estimate the functional groups involved in complexation. In our FT-IR studies, the ($C\equiv N$) and ($C=O$) stretching vibrations in the DDQ species appeared at 2227 and 1678 cm^{-1} , respectively³⁵. In the CT-complexes of the donors (Fig. 4) the two stretching vibrations occurred at 2214–2209 and 1632–1569 cm^{-1} . Such a bathochromic shift could be indicative of a

higher charge density on the carbonyl and cyano groups of the complexed DDQ. Further, the correlation of the $C=O$ stretching frequency of the CT-complexes versus the ionization potentials is excellent (Fig. 5, $r = 0.999$) with positive slope, as expected.

Conclusions :

The experimental results of the CT-complexes formed between the drugs and DDQ in different solvents show that the values of the thermodynamic and spectrophotometric properties are markedly affected by variation of the solvent in which the measurements are carried out. It may be concluded that the acceptor form strong CT-complex of 1 : 1 stoichiometry with the drugs in all the solvents studied. From the trends in the CT-absorption bands, the vertical ionization potential of the drug molecule has been estimated and it is in good agreement with those values computed theoretically by employing MOPAC (PM3) method. The oscillator strength and transition dipole moment of the drug-acceptor CT-complexes have also been determined. The investigated complex is stable and exothermic in nature. The ionization potential of the drug molecule and the heat of complexation data, in several media, may be useful in understanding the binding of drug molecule in real pharmacokinetic study.

Experimental

The pure form of the donor drugs were from various pharmaceutical industries as gift samples and the acceptor DDQ was from Aldrich and were used as received. The structures of the donors are shown below.

Ofloxacin-I

Chlorpheniramine-II

Azacyclonol-III

Indapamide-IV

The solvents used were of spectroscopic grade from BDH, India or SRL, India and used without further purification. The selection of solvents is based in the solubility of the donors and acceptor molecules and such a way to have a wide range of relative permittivity values. The electronic absorption spectra are recorded on a Shimadzu (UV 240, Graphicorn) double beam spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched quartz cells. The temperature of the cell holder was controlled with a water flow. All measurements were performed by using freshly prepared solutions.

The molecular orbital package, MOPAC 2000 version 1.11 was used for computational analysis. The MOPAC program is based on quantum chemical principles, and calculates chemical properties such as electron density, HOMO, LUMO, heat of formation of molecules etc. In the present MOPAC calculation, we used, for the theoretical calculation of the ionization potential of the donors, the PM3 semi-empirical parameters developed by Stewart³⁶.

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